

Monarch Initiative's response to the

RFI for the NIH Policy for

Data Management and Sharing and Supplemental

DRAFT Guidance

Section I: Purpose

While the proposed policy is an improvement over baseline, it still lacks the specificity and enforceability that would ensure that resources are not only shared but also useful. For example, while the policy includes requirement of sharing plans as part of JIT, there is no description as to the process for their review and approval. Further, there really is not much guidance into what constitutes the most critical elements of quality resource sharing and reuse, which should be the attributes against which the Plan will be evaluated.

The proposed policy attempts to describe the importance of resource sharing to society; it might be more compelling if it drew more from the experiences garnered from numerous previous large NIH collaborative data sharing programs or from community recommendations such as from the [Moonshot Blue Ribbon panel on data sharing](#). What is needed isn't more box checking, but rather to fundamentally change the research landscape, elevating the practice of resource sharing to its rightful place alongside the usual suspects of hypotheses, reagents, and results. The overall shared goal will be to create a network effect - or the "data ecosystem" as described in the [blue ribbon recommendations](#).

Section II: Definitions

Enhance the definition of "Data Management." As described above, this definition does not include the fact that data management must be an iterative and integral part of ongoing research requiring specialized skills to ensure that the quality of shared data is fundamentally useful and reusable where possible.

Enhance the definition of "Data Sharing". Specifics should be included such as access mechanisms (API, data downloads, etc.), archival plans and persistence (DOIs or other persistent identifiers), standards and data harmonization (checklists, models, ontologies), and licensing (use rights, flow-through terms).

Add specific definitions for standards and data and resource licensing.

Add definition for software, standards, clinical instruments, and other resource types. The "Plan" should be a data and resource sharing plan.

Section III: Scope

Scope should make clear that the policy continues to apply for scientific resources produced by funding in whole or in part from NIH after the NIH funding period is over.

Scope should make clear that these requirements apply not just to research project grants and contracts, but most other forms of requests for support that will lead to the creation of scientific data and resources. This includes cooperative agreements, career grants, fellowships, scholarships, and training grants.

Scope should make it clear that these requirements apply not just to primary data but also to derived data and to other products of research including software, standards, protocols, reagents, devices etc. Each of these should be defined in the definitions. Further, it should be noted in the Plan how such things will interact - for example, often specific data types may be inaccessible without specific software tools.

Scope should include a statement about human subjects data sharing. While obviously human subjects privacy rules and ethics must be adhered to, this needs to become less of a barrier to data sharing properly. Improved recommendations and processes for sharing human subjects data must be provided and incentivized by NIH. Further, there is a fundamental right of patients to share their data with proper informed consent. Within the scope, it must be clear that harm to patients can come from both sharing and not sharing their data and proper sharing and risk mitigation must both be taken into account.

Section IV: Effective Date(s)

NIH might consider a phased rollout, for instance:

- **Month 2:** Resource Sharing Plans are strongly advised for all new submissions
- **Month 6:** Resource Sharing Plans are required for all new submissions
- **Month 12:** Resource Sharing Plans are incorporated into scored review components for all new submissions. Instructions to reviewers are updated to reflect this.
- In time, it would be optimal to transition from a template to some kind of formal registration of proposed products; structured representations would improve not only enforceability but also potentially improve discoverability and impact tracking.

Regardless of the timeline, the specific roll out plans and responsibilities must be clearly detailed to ensure quality compliance while retaining good will.

Section V: Requirements

It is not entirely clear what the requirements section is aiming to address (that all grants must have one? We suggest the following two aspects be considered:

The data sharing plan **MUST** be part of the review criteria. Review panels must include data science expertise in standards/reusability/dissemination/archiving. Further, review and endorsement of the plan during JIT should be necessarily be performed by experts in data sharing, data standardization, and data archiving.

We applaud the notion that “The Plan will become a Term and Condition of the Notice of Award.” However, this aforementioned expert review process should similarly occur during grant reporting periods in order to determine adherence to the plan and make recommendations for updates to the plan as the work proceeds. There is not enough detail about what the process will be for determining whether or not the Terms and Conditions have been met.

Section VI: Data Management and Sharing Plans

We advise that the policy specifically mandate that Data and Resource sharing plans:

- Be required for all proposals (regardless of amount or nature of the award);
- Be incorporated into the review (Guidance to reviewers on how to score review criteria such as significance and approach should include review of the Data Management and Sharing Plan);
- Include descriptions of any genuine ethical or legal constraints that would preclude or limit the sharing of data, if applicable;
- Have required sections corresponding to all expected products (see sections below)
- Require applicants to describe their proposed use of existing resources, standards, etc.

We have published in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3604521>) our most recently submitted sharing plan in the hopes that it could serve as an example of a format that could prompt applicants to be more strategic and thoughtful about the downstream use of their work.

We also advise that all progress reports for funded projects include a description of progress toward the sharing plans described in the proposal.

The plan should also delineate the different rationales for sharing data. Some data is designed to be directly reusable in downstream applications, whereas other data is shared to promote reproducibility and transparency. These two rationales exist in a spectrum. However, the process used to make data reusable in downstream applications differs from simpler reproducibility endeavors - a more robust curation, metadata, quality assurance, identifier, and persistence strategy needs to be employed in addition to methodological documentation and cost management for storage or processing.

Finally, there does not seem to be a recognition regarding the need to record provenance or attribution of the data or other artifacts. It is critically important to know how the data was created and where it came from in the context of data reuse. Further, the use of credit systems such as the newly developed [Contribution Role Ontology and Contributor Attribution Model](#) can incentivize sharing and recognize team contributions in addition to adding to the provenance.

Section VII: Compliance and Enforcement

As currently written, the compliance and enforcement does not appear to be much stronger than the status quo. As described above, there should be an opportunity for investigators at the time of JIT to improve and finalize their Data and Resource Sharing plan in response to expert reviews. The revised Plans should be made public alongside abstracts, with contact information regarding what to do to report violations or to simply make suggestions. Often times one community is not aware of standardized best practices in another. Therefore a dedicated data sharing navigator may be warranted to help investigators, especially in the early phases of this policy rollout. Finally, the consequences of a serious violation need to be made clear and should be equally applied regardless of stature or institution. The sharing of taxpayer-funded data and resources should be mandatory and the consequences for not doing so should be as significant as data fabrication or other scientific misconduct. Similar to not releasing funds until public access policy has been demonstrated, so should adherence to resource sharing plans.

[Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Allowable Costs for Data Management and Sharing](#)

Quality preparation of data for actual reuse takes time and money. Researchers should not only have to justify the process and expense, but the budget and / or budget justification should have a section identifying what requested resources would be utilized for this purpose. Just as they would with other budget categories, reviewers should consider whether proposed allowances are appropriate and adequate to ensure compliance with the policy. The type of expertise required to curate, provision quality metadata, harmonize data or otherwise standardize and disseminate data is its own specialized skill. Given that most researchers do not recognize this a priori, it should be a recommendation that funds be included for such activities and/or staff with these expertise throughout the life of the proposed work and beyond. Costs that can be accrued during the funding period that enable data preservation post-funding period should be allowed and recommended where needed.

Supplemental DRAFT Guidance: Elements of a NIH Data Management and Sharing Plan

Useful products of NIH funded research extend well beyond data alone. Sections should be included for each of the following and the scope of each section should be defined together with an example. To ensure that the policy can be enforced without unnecessary delays, implementation could start out as a data sharing document template; however, ultimately it would be better to develop a simple system dedicated to capturing and tracking research outputs, and for assessing compliance downstream.

- Type of resource (eg. Software (including algorithms), Data (including images), Standards (including terminologies, data exchange formats), Protocols, Reagents (including Antibodies, cell lines, animals), Devices)
- What the proposed funding covers:
 - Creation of a new resource (eg. generation of Primary Data, or development of brand new software)
 - Enhancement (eg annotation/curation of existing data, improvement of software)
 - Derivation (secondary use of existing data)
- Title of resource
- Problem that the resource addresses
- Proposed repository and / or registration venue of resource
- Existing standards proposed to be used
- URLs where resource is described if applicable
- Proposed or existing license of resource
- Legal and ethical implications, if any

While it is worthwhile for the policy to include information regarding data types (e.g. rationale for which data will be preserved, what level of processing will be performed, etc.), the policy lacks the actual recommendations for describing data standardization. While “Identifying metadata” is described, this is vague and unenforceable. The plans for standardizing data must be included.

Resource sharing plans must identify the standards that applicants propose to use in order to describe and exchange data. If new standards or ontologies are needed, the lack of existing ones must be documented and communities to advise or contribute to new development should be indicated. Plans to perform compliance testing against standards should be provided.

There are no recommendations regarding identifiers. Quality provisioning and use of identifiers is a key component of making data FAIR (in all categories of FAIR). We highly recommend that the NIH provide guidance for identifiers and require including this in the Plan. We have published [identifier best practices](#) based on our extensive efforts to reuse data from public knowledgebases and databases.

While we share the desire to make the plans easily digested, we feel it is unreasonable to limit the plans to two pages. The majority of data sharing plans that we (as experts in data reuse and data sharing), feel obligated to supply to adequately cover our plans - provided at the same level of granularity as the rest of the proposed work - are often longer than 2 pages (see our published example at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3604521>). A structured document format or dedicated platform would make it less onerous for applicants to prepare while also making it easier for reviewers to assess, and for compliance officers to follow up.

Other Considerations Relevant to this DRAFT Policy Proposal

In designing grant review processes, it is really important to recognize that the scientific workforce is not limited to those who themselves have been awarded funds. Peer review for data science and data sharing aspects of

research is often not assessable by domain experts found on such panels. We highly recommend that the grant and Plan review processes leverage experts in these areas, which is really no different than soliciting reviews from domain experts for a given research topic.

While the idea of FAIR has created community awareness that is to be applauded, more needs to be done to realize those goals. From the perspective of those of us in the business of reusing large numbers of data sources and aiming ourselves to make data more reusable, one needs to be cautious about “FAIR-washing.” The policy recommendations should therefore focus on the important, specific, and enforceable practices that truly make resources more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. For example, we refer the reader to our earlier FAIR-TLC response to RFI NOT-OD-16-133 Metrics to Assess Value of Biomedical Digital Repositories. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.203295>